

GES4SEAS POLICY BRIEF #6

GOOD ENVIRONMENTAL STATUS – WHAT IS IT AND HOW DO WE KNOW WHEN IT IS ACHIEVED?

How can this Policy Brief support you?

Marine management needs to define who requires and can achieve a successfully managed environment. It selects the tools for that management and the indicators to assess whether the environment has been successfully managed. Marine practitioners need to understand the overall vision and policy requirements involved in using and managing the marine environment. This applies to both those carrying out marine activities and those managing and regulating them, and those protecting the seas. In the case of Europe, this requires considering the way in which approaches and tools have developed since the adoption of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) in 2008 (and further amendments) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) in 2014, as well as tools required for the Ocean Pact and the upcoming Ocean Act. All stakeholders should be aware of, firstly, the 11 MSFD Descriptors, their criteria and indicators, which are integral parts of determining whether an area is in Good Environmental Status (GES). Secondly, they need to be aware of the drawbacks and current challenges in the monitoring, assessment and reporting for GES.

Key Messages

Given that the EU Marine Strategy and the MSFD must be based on the Ecosystem-based Approach (EBA, setting the priorities/policies), then GES is achieved by Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) which is operationalised through management and governance ([link to policy brief 1](#)).

EBM requires the use of tools, including legal, technological and economic instruments, now termed Ecosystem-Based Technical Measures (EBTM) through Ecosystem-based Science (EBS) ([link to policy brief 1](#)).

The MSFD, currently focused on local pressures, must explicitly integrate climate change as a cross-cutting pressure affecting all descriptors rather than treating it as force majeure ([link to policy brief 2](#)).

The determination of GES should assess the changes due to not only single activities and their pressures, but especially cumulative effects ([link to policy brief 3](#)).

The determination of GES needs to include setting and applying spatial targets and thresholds, and assessing tipping points and trajectories of changes to the status of seas ([link to policy brief 4](#)).

If GES is not achieved, then Programmes of Measures (PoM, including EBTM) need to be enacted ([link to policy brief 3](#)).

Achieving GES will ensure ocean health both for the natural system and the well-being of society, thereby operationalising the new One Health concept ([link to policy brief 5](#)).

Many national, regional, European and global initiatives are aimed at protecting the oceans ([link to policy brief 7](#)).

Narrative of the problem, with GES4SEAS examples

The MSFD definition says that “GES is the environmental status of marine waters where these provide ecologically diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are intrinsically clean, healthy and productive, and the use of the marine environment is at a level that is sustainable, thus safeguarding the potential for uses and activities by current and future generations.”

This should lead to a clear operational definition, e.g. “GES is achieved when physical-chemical-biological (including contaminants, invasive species, litter and noise) and hydrographical conditions are maintained at a level where the structuring components of the ecosystem are present and functioning, enabling the system to be resistant (an ability to withstand stress) and resilient (an ability to recover after a stressor) to harmful effects of human pressures/activities, where biodiversity is maintained and provides the ecosystem services that deliver societal benefits in a sustainable way. This implies that pressures associated with uses cumulatively do not hinder the ecosystem components in order to retain their natural diversity, productivity and dynamic ecological processes, and where recovery is rapid and sustained if one or more pressure ceases, and where the system can recover from a tipping point and the previous exceedance of the assimilative capacity”.

The hierarchy of the 11 MSFD Descriptors to achieve GES, i.e. that D1 and D4 appear the most important and logically these are met if all others are met and they fail if any of others fail; however, note that Member States assess and report GES for each Descriptor separately; climate change has been added to the MSFD Descriptors as an overall suite of pressures which ultimately affect all other Descriptors.

Indicators for determining GES are associated with uncertainty that stems from natural variability of observations in time and space as well as sampling-specific variability. EBM should be based on assessing whether GES is achieved with high confidence. Hence the need for quantifying uncertainty associated with indicators, criteria and descriptors, using NEAT (Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool), in the Tikta software (see [GES4SEAS Policy Brief #3](#)).

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) provides a key data infrastructure for GES assessment, offering harmonised datasets linked to MSFD descriptors and criteria. An inventory of MSFD-EMODnet links has been integrated into Tikta to support data accessibility and use.

Indicators of success require policies and plans such as environmental targets as well as regulatory standards and guidelines. Marine management should aim for sustainable outcomes based on government policy, to satisfy public demands and using the advice and assessments by natural and social scientists.

There are three types of 'who' is involved: in marine management (i) who requires a successfully managed environment such as the public who are beneficiaries and influencers; (ii) who is responsible to carry-out and monitor the programmes and regulate humans and their activities as mandated by government, such as administrators and regulators, and (iii) who will be implementing the management measures.

Policy implications

European Directives

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), GES reporting and PoMs;
- Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD);
- Natura 2000 Directives (to compare GES with Favourable Conservation Status);
- Nature Restoration Regulation (identifying risk areas/habitats/ species is key to determine fit-for-purpose restoration measures that secure ecosystem services and associated benefits);
- Water Framework Directive (catchment health as ecological and chemical status, (also GES and GCS);
- European Ocean Pact & Ocean Act
- All other marine environmental regulations.

Other Policy / International Objectives

- Regional Seas Conventions, reporting the status;
- UN Convention on Law of the Sea;
- Convention on Biological Diversity;
- UN Convention on Climate Change;
- European Environment Agency (EEA, including Marine Messages 3);
- All other marine environmental agreements;
- All Sustainable Development Goals relevant to the oceans

Beyond the State of Art

GES4SEAS has contributed to operationalizing the ways in which policy-makers and managers can progress towards GES. We have proposed ways to harmonize the Member States reporting on GES for the MSFD, making comparable their results across regional seas, for pressures, state and environmental impacts. This approach has started to be used by the Joint Research Centre, allowing rapid and efficient comparisons of the reports. In addition, in GES4SEAS, we have developed Tikta, a software that includes the NEAT (Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool) assessment method, which can be used flexibly by Member States in MSFD assessments to show progress towards achieving GES. In addition, other tools such as MAMBO, which is targeted to HAB management, or Pressure2Eco, which allows identifying potential activities/pressures responsible for non-GES. We have also shown that research evidence, such as that of top-predator success stories showing that bycatch mitigation, protected areas, fisheries regulation, sustained monitoring and stakeholder collaboration can reverse declines under ecosystem-based management, provide innovative progress towards managing the ocean towards GES.

However, for coherent management of EU seas, comparable assessments across Member States and EU-wide overview of the status and MSFD progress are essential. GES4SEAS developed pressure, state, and impact indices, by integrating available MSFD data reported by EU Member States. For the first time, in GES4SEAS MSFD data have been used to produce a European regional assessment which shows that most regions are far from demonstrating GES, as they are suffering from intense pressures and impacts. Significant knowledge gaps were identified, particularly in the eastern Mediterranean. This highlights the urgent need for enhanced ecological monitoring and setting environmental targets to improve the poor state of European seas, advocating stronger regional cooperation and standardized methodologies.

Key Facts

The ongoing revision of the MSFD and MSPD, and the integration of GES thresholds and spatial targets into the European Ocean Act, will strengthen MSP and address climate, biodiversity and pollution challenges.

Harmonising monitoring, assessment and reporting across EU legislation is essential to ensure coherence, reduce duplication and provide solid evidence for marine management.

The outputs and outcomes should include scientific research, science advisory processes, reporting to the government and the public as well as programme performance evaluations including conforming and compliance.

There is concern regarding combining the indicators and reporting GES for each descriptor and ecological component; this leads to challenges in monitoring, assessment and reporting.

Implementing the MSFD and achieving GES is the means to fulfil the Marine Strategy and secure a sustainable future for the oceans.

It is necessary to consider whether assessing and reporting GES separately for each Descriptor or ecological component is conducive to achieving a One Health approach, implementing the Ocean Act and committing to the Ocean Pact with a European Ocean Health Index.

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References from GES4SEAS

For GES4SEAS resources and references click this [link](#) or scan this QR code.

For references from outside GES4SEAS see:

Borja, Á., et al., 2010. Marine Pollution Bulletin 60: 2175-2186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2010.09.026>

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Datasets used | MSFD reporting data explorer | WISE Marine Marine Information System for Europe Franco, A., et al., 2021. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2779/972595>.

For additional resources from the GES4SEAS project, visit the web page: <https://www.ges4seas.eu>

For more information about these and other GES4SEAS publications, scan the QR code

